

If you would be a non-human, who/what would you like to be?

„The biodiversity discourse generates and mobilizes a complex network of actors: from international organizations to mostly Western NGOs; from transnational bioprospectors, extending over indigenous communities, to social movements (Escobar 1998).

It creates (or denies) access to resources, depending on whether biodiversity is framed as “common heritage of humanity” (in the economic sense of “global commons”) or rather as a good under the sovereign control of nation states or even local communities (Turnhout et al. 2013).

Eventually, it privileges certain forms of knowledge, while delegitimizing and therefore marginalizing others (Vadrot2014).“ (Mangelsdorf et al. 2016, p.6)

1.4. The PigeonBlog team of human beings, pigeons, and electronic technologies. Photograph by Deborah Forster for PigeonBlog. Courtesy of Robert Modifler, artistic executor for Beavrits da Costa.

Workshop 1, February 1st, 2023

10:00-10:15 Welcome and introduction

10:15-10:45 Case study exercise

10:45-11:15 Case study reporting and discussion part 1

11:15-11:30 Coffee break

11:00-12:15 Case study reporting and discussion part 2

12:15-12:45 Reflections and questions from critical friends

12:45-13:00 Feedback and outlook

Air pollution in South California + working pigeons --> environmental justice: grass roots scientific data gathering (racing pigeons gather real-time pollution data not accessible to official instruments.
The pigeon backpack = GPS + sensors + microcontrollers (--> SMS)
Pigeons as "living co-producers" --> multispecies project

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/361424804_Bridging_Neurodiversity_and_Open_Scholarship_How_Shared_Values_Can_Guide_Best_Practices_for_Research_Integrity_Social_Justice_and_Principled_Education

Adapted from cccwvlab @ghindachworth

Feedback WS1

Thank you very much - this was a very valuable workshop! I have learned about CSs and their intersectionality aspects a lot!

Thank you for the feedbacks and critical point related to the case study

very nice and useful opportunity to learn more about the cases

New perspectives and/or learnings I am taking from the workshop ...

Perhaps we could start to link CSs to interventions?

if we are working with digital tool as facilitation, it will be a good idea to share the link to the tool perhaps a day earlier. just to see the intensity of the work that are expected

perhaps a concise case story about the pigeons-case of Haraway would help us to better understand intersectionality as an analytical perspective

What could be improved for the next workshop?

Case Study:

<p>Case Study Description Describe your case study in a nutshell - add a photo if you can.</p> <p>4</p>		
<p>Why? Why is it important to implement the transformative change linked to your case study? (Both for biodiversity and people involved)</p> <p>5</p>		
	<p>Capacities: What can help you to set up inclusive learning communities? What can support actors in your case study? What capacities are there yet already?</p> <p>6</p>	

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